

Analysis of Strategy to Improve the Competitiveness of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group Medan

Riswanda Pranata¹, Isfenti Sadalia², Yeni Absah²

^{1,2}Magister of Management, Postgraduate School of University of Sumatera Utara

Corresponding Author: Riswanda Pranata

ABSTRACT

Comprehensive analysis of the environment is important to do in recognition of the various types of internal and external forces that affect the organization. The purpose of this study is to analyze the strengths and weaknesses (internal environment) of PT LunataTeknokindo Group, analyze opportunities and threats (external environment) of PT LunataTeknokindo Group and analyze the most appropriate marketing strategies that must be carried out by PT LunataTeknokindo Group to win the competition. This research uses a qualitative research method with descriptive research type. For this research the key informants were 1) Commissioner 2) Director 3) Director of IT 4) Sales Marketing Manager 5) Administration Manager 6) Financial Manager. The total value of IFE is 3.23 and the total value of EFE is 3.16. The total value of IFE and EFE is obtained from the sum of the scores on each factor, where the score is obtained from the multiplication between the average rating and the average weight for each factor. This value shows the position of quadrant I, which shows the strategy needed for the company today is "grow and build strategy".

Keywords: SWOT, IFE, EFE

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has the fastest growth rate of IT spending in the Asia Pacific region. The Indonesia Data Center (IDC) sees that Indonesia will rank at the top with an estimated growth rate of 13.4%. The software segment is expected to show the fastest growth of 9.4% in 2017 because companies in the banking industry and

securities invest more in applications, infrastructure, and software. With the rapid growth of IT, managers within the organization are required to think strategically about the organization's competitive position and capabilities and the influence of the development of the external environment on the organization. This is done to win competition in business.

The Indonesian Chamber of Commerce and Industry noted that the number of digital startups in Indonesia reached 2,000 people. The amount is claimed to be the highest number in Southeast Asia. In fact, in 2020, the number of digital startups in Indonesia has the opportunity to jump to 200,000 people. The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Industry in Indonesia in the past five years grew 9.98-10.7% per year, almost double the national economic growth of 4.79-6.56%. Related to this, Business, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) as part of the business requires a strategy to be able to win a competitive advantage with changes in the environment both external and internal. One of the SMEs in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is PT LunataTeknokindo Group. Is a company engaged in the field of Information Technology and consultants focusing on the service of goods and services in the form of hardware, software and networking.

Based on PT LunataTeknokindo Group's revenue data in 2015 and 2017 the company's projects experienced an increase in revenue, while the previous year the

company experienced a decrease in revenue. In addition, the company experienced a decline in retail sales and in 2014 to 2015 and in 2017. So far, to face competition, PT LunataTeknokindo Group has undertaken a strategy to increase value or value added and then the company sells value not price. This strategy is considered the most flexible strategy because it can be applied depending on the ability of the company. One of the reasons for the decline in company revenue is the presence of competitors who have long been in this market so that they have a brand in the minds of consumers with a high enough market share.

Opportunities and intense business competition in the existing IT consulting industry require PT LunataTeknokindo Group to anticipate it through the formulation of strategies that enable the company to continue to grow and develop in the future.

STRATEGY

Wheelen & Hunger (2012) said the company's strategy is a unit plan (master plan) which contains how the company achieves its mission and objectives. There are three types of strategies, namely (1) the corporate level strategy describes the overall

direction of the company's growth and management of various business lines and products. This strategy must meet three main requirements: stability, growth, and savings, (2) business-level strategies occur at the business unit or product level. This strategy emphasizes increasing the competitive position of products in related industries or market segments of business units, and (3) functional level strategies are approaches used at the functional level to achieve company and business unit goals by maximizing resource productivity.

The goal of strategy management is to find and create new and different opportunities for tomorrow, long-term planning instead trying to optimize tomorrow's trends based on current trends (David, 2011). The strategy management process are:

Strategy Formulation

Strategy formulation includes developing vision and mission, identifying organizational opportunities and threats, determining internal strengths and weaknesses, creating Long-term goals, initiating alternative strategies and choosing specific strategies to achieve (David, 2011).

Table 1 Analytical Framework for Strategy Formulation

Stage 1 : INPUT STEP				
External Factor Evaluation (EFE) Matrix		Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM)		Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix
Stage 2 : MATCHING STEP				
Strengths–Weaknesses– Opportunities–Threats (SWOT) Matrix	Strategic Position and Action Evaluation (SPACE) Matrix	Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix	Internal– External (IE) Matrix	Grand Strategy Matrix
Stage 3 : DECISION STEP				
Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM)				

ANALYSIS OF THE EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT

1. Macro Environment

Macro environment consists of factors originating from outside the company and are generally unrelated and have no direct effect on the company. These factors are as follows (Thompson, 2010):

Geographical

Distribution is influenced by geographical location, level of income and trends within the geographical environment.

Social and Culture

Social factors that influence a company include the beliefs, values, attitudes, opinions, and lifestyle of the community, which develops from cultural, demographic, religious, educational, and ethnic conditions. When social attitudes change, the demand for various types of products and services will also change.

Law and Government

Political factors determine the legal parameters and rules in which companies

must operate. Political restrictions imposed on companies are usually imposed through fair trade decisions, antitrust laws, tax programs, minimum wage rules, pricing policies, and various other measures aimed at protecting employees, consumers, the general public, and the environment. Because such regulations are usually restrictive, they tend to reduce the company's profit potential. But some political actions are designed to benefit and protect companies such as patent laws, government subsidies, and product research funds.

Technological Factors

To help develop the innovation process, a company must be aware that technological changes might affect its industry. Adaptation of the latest and creative technology can create the possibility of new products or quality improvement on existing products or as a supporter of manufacturing and marketing processes.

The economy

Economic factors are related to the nature and direction of the economy in which a company operates. Because consumption patterns are influenced by the prosperity of various market segments, each company must consider economic trends in segments that affect its industry.

Competitive Environment

The competitive environment is a character and competitive power in the industry that is operating, each company will have different environmental characteristics with other companies. As for the factors included in the competitive environment, there are supplier strength, substitute products, competitors, consumer strength, and threats from new entrants (Thompson et al., 2010).

ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNAL ENVIRONMENT

According to David (2011) The process of conducting an internal audit is the same as conducting an external audit. Internal audits require the collection and assimilation of information regarding management, marketing, finance and

accounting, production and operations, R&D, and company information systems. The explanation according to David (2011) is as follows:

Management

The management function consists of five basic activities namely planning, organizing, motivating, employee placement and control.

Marketing

Marketing can be defined by defining, anticipating, creating and determining customer needs for products and services. There are seven marketing functions, namely:

Customer analysis, Selling products and services, Product and service planning, Pricing, Distribution, Marketing research, Opportunity analysis.

Finance

Financial conditions are often considered as the best arrears measurement of a company's competitive position and overall attractiveness of investors. Determining the strengths and weaknesses of an organization is important in order to effectively formulate a strategy. Liquidity, leverage, working capital, profitability and use of assets, cash flow, and equity can eliminate some decent elimination strategies.

Production / Operations

The production function of the business consists of all activities that convert inputs into goods and services. Production and operations management is related to inputs, changes and outputs that vary between industries and markets.

Research and Development

Effective management of the R&D function requires strategic and operational partnerships between R&D and other key business functions.

Information System

The purpose of management information systems is to improve the performance of the company by improving the quality of managerial decisions.

COMPETITIVENESS

Corporate competitiveness is the ability of a company to create and formulate

various strategies that can put it in a strategic position and be more profitable when compared to other companies (Tangkilian, 2003). Meanwhile, according to Porter (2012) can be defined as the business ability of a company in the industry to deal with various environments encountered. Competitiveness is determined by the competitive advantage of a company and is very dependent on the level of

relative resources it has or we call it competitive advantage.

SWOT ANALYSIS

Banihashemi & Rejaei (2016) said the SWOT analysis tool was used by researchers to develop strategies based on the strengths and weaknesses of the company and take advantage of opportunities and avoid threats.

Tabel 2 Analysis SWOT

SWOT ANALYSIS	Opportunities	Threats
Strengths	How do you leverage your strengths to benefit from your opportunities?	How do you use your strengths to minimize the impact of threats?
Weaknesses	How do you ensure your weaknesses will not stop you from opportunities?	How will you fix weaknesses that can make threats have a real impact?

This gives businesses a clear view of the benefits they get from competitors and their possible vulnerabilities. This is mainly used by businesses to create effective business plans / strategies and for comparison with competitors.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Indicator	Dimension	Factor
1.1 Demand and supply 1.2 Inflation 1.3 Exchange Rates 1.4 Interest Rates 1.5 Economic Growth / Changes in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) 1.6 Community Income (income) 1.7 Prices in the Market (Price) 1.8 Public consumption expenditure (consumption)	Non Direct 1. Economy	External
2.1 Government Policy 2.2 Consumer protection laws 2.3 Law of Business	2. Law and Government	
3.1 Lifestyle 3.2 Consumer tastes 3.3 Community Culture 3.4 Community trust and confidence or community attitudes and beliefs 3.5 Political structure. Community education	3. Social and Culture	
4.1 Internet 4.2 New Technology Development	4. Technology	
1.1 Office location 1.2 Regional conditions to support the distribution of goods to consumers, as well as from suppliers to companies	5. Geography	
1.1 Consumer 1.2 Competitors 1.3 Supplier 1.4 New Arrivals 1.5 Substitution Goods	Direct:	Internal
1.1 Employee turn over 1.2 Organizational structure 1.3 Recruitment of employees 1.4 HR skills 1.5 Educational background of employees 1.6 Experience	Human Resources	
2.1 Market reach 2.2 Pricing 2.3 Promotion	Marketing	
3.1 Supply of raw materials Production capacity	Production/ Operational	
3.2 Enterprise and product development efforts	Research and development	
3.3 Business integration with the internet	Information Systems	

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method is a technique or procedure used to analyze empirical evidence in activities to confirm or refute previous concepts (Zikmund et al., 2010). This study uses qualitative research methods with the type of descriptive research. Spradley in Sugiyono (2014) uses social situation to refer to a population consisting of three elements: places, actors, and activities that interact synergistically. Samples in qualitative research are not named respondents, but as resource persons, participants, teams and teachers in research. Sugiyono (2014). For this research the key informants were 1) Commissioner 2) Director 3) Director of IT 4) Sales Marketing Manager 5) Administration Manager 6) Financial Manager. Data collection using qualitative observation is fundamentally naturalistic in which this technique can be applied in the natural context of an event among actors who naturally want to participate in interactions (Denzin and Lincoln, 2009). Technical analysis of the data is by conducting a SWOT analysis that compares the external factors of opportunities (threats) and threats (threats) with the internal factors of the strengths and weaknesses. The analytical framework for strategy formulation consists of the External Factor Evaluation (EFE) matrix and the Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) and Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) matrix. In this stage it is called the

input stage. Phase 2 is referred to as the sweeping stage, focusing on making alternative strategies including the SWOT matrix, SPACE matrix, BCG Matrix, IE matrix, and the Grand Strategy Matrix. Stage 3 is called decision making involving a single technique, QSPM.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the IFE matrix and EFE matrix, it can be arranged later in the IE matrix. The total value of IFE is 3.23 and the total value of EFE is 3.16. The total value of IFE and EIEFE is obtained from the sum of the scores on each factor, where the score is obtained from the multiplication between the average rating and the average weight for each factor. This value shows the position of quadrant I, which shows the strategy needed for the company today is a grow and build strategy. Grow and build strategy shows that the company needs a strategy to grow better and can develop the company to be better.

Table 3 Matrix IE

	Strong 3.0 – 4.0	Normal 2.0 – 2.99	Weak 1.0 – 1.99
High 3.0 – 4.0	I	II	III
Middle 2.0 – 2.99	IV	V	VI
Low 1.0 – 1.99	VII	VIII	IX

Based on this, the strategy design of PT LunataTeknokindo Group, namely the SWOT Matrix can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4 SWOT Matrix

SWOT MATRIX	Strenght (S)	Weakness (W)
	PT Lunata Teknokindo Group has a structured organizational structure (structure and relationship between each section and position), so that each employee has clear job details.	There are still employees coming in and out.
	To ensure that employees who join PT Lunata Teknokindo have the best abilities, skills and knowledge in the IT field, the company has a selection phase in the recruitment process that is targeted and qualified.	Company attention to employees is still considered lacking by some employees.
	Employees at PT Lunata Teknokindo Group have the best knowledge in their fields.	
	Employees at PT Lunata Teknokindo Group have the best skills in their fields.	
	PT Lunata Teknokindo Group employees have a good educational background.	
	PT Lunata Teknokindo Group employees have good experience in their respective fields and are selected based on the selection and directed process.	
	The market reach of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group in all regions of Medan, outside the city and can be reached throughout North	

	<p>Sumatra.</p> <p>PT Lunata Teknokindo Group always offers product prices according to market conditions.</p> <p>Through its information technology capabilities, the company promotes retail products and projects of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group.</p> <p>Because PT Lunata's suppliers are spread throughout Indonesia, so, the supply of raw materials from suppliers for retail and project businesses is always guaranteed.</p> <p>To improve and develop the capabilities of the products and services offered, the company continues to take steps to develop and continuously improve retail products and projects.</p> <p>The location of the PT Lunata Teknokindo Group office is quite strategic for consumers and suppliers.</p> <p>The relationship between consumers and the community with PT Lunata is quite good</p> <p>PT Lunata Teknokindo Group has suppliers who are ready to supply the company's needs at any time.</p> <p>Business integration of the internet (Use of the internet in business).</p>	
Opportunity (O) PT Lunata Teknokindo Group	SOStrategy	WOStrategy
<p>Market needs for IT products such as laptops, CCTV and software, drive higher market demand (market demand).</p> <p>Economic growth that will drive an increase in people's income</p> <p>Increasing community income drives higher consumer demand.</p> <p>Product selling prices in the market.</p> <p>A portion of public consumption expenditure is used for IT related needs.</p> <p>Government policies that support the progress of the IT business.</p> <p>Consumer protection law.</p> <p>Changes in people's lifestyle will be the need for IT products</p> <p>Taste for IT products</p> <p>Acceptance of public culture of the existence of IT products.</p> <p>The ability of IT products to help the public in the beliefs they believe.</p> <p>Substitution of leaders (president / regional head).</p> <p>Education on the need for IT products</p> <p>The desire in self to advance to follow the development of the Digital era.</p>	<p>a. Provides high-performance server.</p> <p>b. Organize seminars or knowledge sharing activities for consumers who have the desire to go forward by learning about the use of information technology with PT Lunata Teknokindo Group. Consumers who are included in this activity are potential consumers who are considered interested in being a customer project of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group.</p> <p>c. Conduct a market survey once a month to find out up-to-date consumer tastes.</p>	<p>Providing bonus fee agents and rewards to employees who can attract consumers to become consumers of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group.</p> <p>B) Providing training to employees to become a reliable IT and financial consultant so that consumers can set aside part of their income for IT investment by providing benefits.</p>
Threat (T)	STStrategy	WTStrategy
<p>Inflation on prices of IT products.</p> <p>The current dollar exchange rate against purchasing power for IT products</p> <p>Interest rates (loan interest) on purchasing power for IT products</p> <p>Newcomers to the Industry</p> <p>PT Lunata's competitors are quite a lot</p> <p>PT Lunata's substitution items are quite a lot.</p>	<p>a. Making clear SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) this is done to facilitate, tidy up, and bring order to the work of employees at PT Lunata Teknokindo Group.</p> <p>b. Maintaining the quality of the software of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group by maintaining prices, while maintaining a good relationship with suppliers.</p>	<p>Provide opportunities for self-development and a clear career path for employees who make the best contribution to the company.</p>

SO (Strength and Opportunity) Strategy

SO Strategy uses the company's internal strengths to take advantage of external opportunities. This is a very good position of PT LunataTeknokindo, where the company will be directed to the conditions that allow the company to implement an SO strategy, after previously using the WO, ST and WT strategies. The company's SO strategies are:

- a. Provides high-performance server. PT Lunata in business activities has many customers and market demand for IT

products is quite high. Therefore, serving hundreds of websites, PT Lunata in its operational activities requires a server with high performance. A web server that serves thousands of visitors, a mail server that serves thousands of requests for sending and receiving servers requires quite high server resources. These resources include the processor, memory and hard drive.

- b. Conduct a market survey once a month to find out up-to-date consumer tastes.

Table 5 SO Strategic Plan

Main Strategy	Alternatives Strategy	Execution time
Provides high-performance server	Providing the server is chosen into two alternative choices: 1. Buy a server 2. Renting a server	Provision of high performance can be done within 3 months of the study conducted (giving an estimated time of fund collection).
Market survey (IT business always changes easily) 1. Observe market developments. 2. The level of market competition. (find out PT Lunata ranks in the competition in the IT business).	None	Once every 3 months and carried out by the marketing team of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group.

WO (Weakness and Opportunity) Strategy

The WO strategy aims to correct internal weaknesses by exploiting external opportunities. The company's WO strategy is:

- a. Companies can provide bonus agent fees and rewards to employees who can attract consumers to become consumers of PT LunataTeknokindo Group.
- b. Apart from being an IT consultant, employees need to become reliable financial consultants. In addition to offering IT products, employees can provide input related to financial management to consumers for investment in the use of IT products, so that consumers can set aside part of their income for IT investments by providing benefits such as holiday ticket bonuses to Overseas.

Table 6 WO Strategic Plan

Main Strategy	Alternatives Strategy	Execution time
Agent fee and reward bonuses (bonus given 2% of each contract value agreed with consumers by employees)	1. Paying BPJS employee health along with his family (for employees who are already married). 2. Do a Family Gathering.	1. While employees are located and working at PT Lunata Teknokindo Group. 2. Family Gathering is held in 2 times a year.
Marketing employees have two tasks to market and as a financial analyst with the condition that the welfare of employees must be guaranteed financially. (1 Employee 2 Tasks)	Form another division within PT Lunata, the financial consultant section that will work closely with the marketing team. (2 employees, marketing and finance)	This strategy is estimated to be carried out in 2020 this is considered when the company has better financial readiness in 2020

WT (Weakness and Threat) Strategy

The WT strategy is a defensive tactic aimed at reducing internal weaknesses and avoiding external threats. The WT strategies undertaken by PT LunataTeknokindo Group are to provide opportunities for self-development and a clear career path for employees who make the best contribution to the company. For example: the employee attracts many customers in the company, the employee has good business analysis and the employee has the best experience and knowledge.

Table 7 WT Strategic Plan

Main Strategy	Alternatives Strategy	Execution time
1. Opportunity to develop themselves (more tuition, tuition fees borne by the company)	Improve communication with employees, take a coffee break. Leaders can invite employees to discuss the obstacles they face when working and make solutions to problems in an atmosphere of casual chatting.	1. Opportunity to develop themselves for a period of 2 years.
2. Career path (opportunity to become a manager)		2. Proving the ability of employees to better career paths is done every 6 months.
		3. Coffe breaks can be done every 10:00 a.m. 3 times a week.

ST (Strength and Threat) Strategy

The ST Strategy uses the company's strengths to avoid or reduce the influence of external threats. The company's ST strategies are:

1. Making clear SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) this is done to facilitate, tidy up, and bring order to the work of employees at PT LunataTeknokindo Group.
2. Maintaining the quality of the software of PT LunataTeknokindo Group by maintaining prices, while maintaining a good relationship with suppliers.

Table 8 ST Strategic Plan

Main Strategy	Alternatives Strategy	Execution time
SOP	None	The making of SOP is done within 1 month.
Product and service quality	-	As long as the company is still operating

CONCLUSION

1. The opportunities at PT Lunata Teknokindo Group is high market demand for IT. The rapid growth of technology is currently causing an increase in market demand for IT, so the best strategy is needed to meet the needs and desires of consumers.
2. There are several threats from PT LunataTeknokindo Group. But the biggest threat is the dollar exchange rate. The dollar exchange rate is a threat for some products imported from abroad.
3. PT LunataTeknokindo Group's greatest strengths are the skills, knowledge and experience of its employees in the IT.
4. The weakness of PT LunataTeknokindo Group is the high level of employee turnover.

REFERENCE

1. Amstrong, Michael. 2010. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. PT Elexmedia Komputindo. Jakarta.
2. Banihashemi, Sayyid A. dan Rajaei, Z. 2016. *Assessment of Environmental Conditions and Internal Capabilities Affecting University Strategies (IFE, EFE, SWOT & AHP Models)*. International Journal of Asian Social Science, 6(10): 558-567.
3. Bougie, &Sekaran. (2013). *Edisi 5, Research Methods for Business: A skill Building Approach*. New York: John wiley Sons.
4. David, Fred.R. 2011. *ManajemenStrategis: Konsep-Konsep*. EdisiDuabelas. Jakarta: SalembaEmpat.
5. Denzin& Lincoln. 2009. *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Yogyakarta: PustakaPelajar
6. Elyarni, Reza&Hermanto. 2016. Analisis SWOT TerhadapStrategiPemasaranLayanan SAP Express pada PT SAP. *Jurnal Metris*, 17 (2016): 81 – 88.
7. Nandakumar, M.K., A. Ghobadian., dan N. O'Regan. 2011. *Generic Strategies and Performance-Evidence From Manufacturing Firms*. International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management, 222-251.
8. Hunger, J. David danWheelen, Thomas L. 2003. *ManajemenStrategis*. Yogyakarta: PenerbitAndi.
9. Hunger, J.D. danWheelen, T.L. 2012. *Strategic Management and Bussiness Policy: Toward Global Sustainability (13th Edition)*. New York: Pearson
10. Jauch, L.R. danGlueck, W.R. 1997. *ManajemenStrategisdanKebijakan Perusahaan, Edisi IV*. Erlangga, Jakarta.
11. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. 2010. *Dasar-dasar Ekonomika Pembangunan*. UPP STIM YKPN Yogyakarta.
12. Kuncoro, EngkosAchmad. 2010. *AnalisisPerumusanStrategiBisnisPada PT*

- Samudera Nusantara Logistindo*. Binus Business Review Vol.1 No.1 Mei 2010: 169-184.
13. Kotler, Philip & Garry Armstrong. 2010. Prinsip-Prinsip Pemasaran, Jilid 1 dan 2 Edisi Kedua Belas. Jakarta :Erlangga Kotler,
 14. Kotler, Philip & Keller K Lane. 2012. 14 Edition. Marketing Management. New Jersey : Pearson Presentice Hall.
 15. Kotler, Philip, dan Gary Armstrong. 2012. *Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran Edisi 13*. Jilid 1. Erlangga : Jakarta.
 16. Kotler, Keller. 2012. *Marketing Management, 14th*, Pearson Education.
 17. Lindawati, Tuty, Christiananta. B, & Ellitan. L. 2014. Determining Basis For The Position Of Competitive Advantage And The Choice Of Strategic Alternatives In Widya Mandala Catholic University Of Surabaya. ISSN-L: 2223-9553, ISSN: 2223-9944 Vol. 5 No. 1.
 18. Nandakumar, M.K., A. Ghobadian., dan N. O'Regan. 2011. *Generic Strategies and Performance-Evidence From Manufacturing Firms*. International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management, 222-251.
 19. Mujahid, Anas., Isharyani M.E & Widada, Dharma. 2018. Analisis Strategi Pemasaran Menggunakan Metode Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrik (QSPM) Studi Kasus : Borneo Project. Jurnal Rekayasa Sistem Industri Volume 7 No 2 Oktober 2018.
 20. Rezazadeh, Siavash, et al. 2017. *Evaluation of the Strategic Factors of the Management of Protected Areas Using SWOT Analysis—Case Study: Bashgol Protected Area-Qazvin Province*. Open Journal of Ecology, 2017, 7, 55-68.
 21. Setyorini, Hany, Effendi Mas'ud & Santoso Imam. 2016. Analisis Strategi Pemasaran Menggunakan Matriks SWOT dan QSPM (Studi Kasus: Restoran WS Soekarno Hatta Malang). *Industria: Jurnal Teknologi dan Manajemen Agroindustri* Volume 5 Nomor 1: 46-53.
 22. Sugiyono. 2014. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta
 23. Sukanta., Sari D.A & Darajat, A.A. 2018. Peningkatan Pada Analisis Strategi Pemasaran Produk Dies DI PT KLM. *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sains Indonesia (JRMSI) | Vol 9, No. 1*.
 24. Thompson, J. A., Strickland, A. J. And Gamble, E.J. 2010. *Crafting and Executing Strategy, Seventeenth Edition*. Mc Graw-Hill/Irwin, Inc., New.
 25. Windyatri, Anggira., Darsono & Adi, R. Kunto. 2017. Strategi Pemasaran Dalam Meningkatkan Volume Penjualan Kecap Manis Di PT Lombok Gandaria Kabupaten Karanganyar. *AGRISTA : Vol. 5 No. 3 September 2017 : 268-278*.
 26. Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., dan Griffin, M.. 2010. *Business Research Methods*. South Western: Cengage Learning, 8th Edition.
 27. Zeta, Erna. 2006. Laporan Ekonomi Bulanan. Edisi Juli. Jakarta : Kamar Dagang dan Industri Indonesia (Kadin).

How to cite this article: Pranata R, Sadalia I, Absah Y. Analysis of strategy to improve the competitiveness of PT Lunata Teknokindo Group Medan. International Journal of Research and Review. 2020; 7(7): 127-135.
